

Mapping Open Educational Content on AI Ethics: A Scoping Review.

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Background

As AI is expected to increasingly affect human cognition and behavior, the need for practical ethics guidance has become increasingly critical (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence [HLEG], 2019). The AIOLIA project responds to this challenge by aiming to operationalize AI ethics through the development of inclusive, interdisciplinary training materials, developed in close partnership with academic institutions, industry actors, and global policy networks. A key part of this effort involves identifying and developing accessible educational resources. This scoping review maps the current landscape of openly available AI ethics learning materials.

Rationale

A growing body of literature and guidelines has proposed ethical principles and values in response to the challenges posed by the rapid emergence of AI systems. However, translating these overarching frameworks into practice remains a challenge. The success of this operationalization depends particularly on the development of well-targeted educational resources. Although a wide range of AI ethics educational materials are openly accessible, their breadth, usability, and pedagogical quality have not yet been systematically examined.

Objectives

The objective of this scoping review is to identify and map openly available educational and training materials related to AI ethics. Specifically, the review will:

- Map resources that are free, publicly accessible, and explicitly designed for educational or training purposes.
- Examine their pedagogical design, including learning objectives, competences targeted, and instructional strategies.
- Identify the ethical concepts and AI-related issues addressed, as well as assessment and reflection components.
- Map the intended audiences (higher education students, professionals) and application domains.
- Assess the breadth, accessibility, and originality of such materials, with a focus on resources published from 2022 onward.
- Highlight strengths, gaps, and areas for further development to inform the AIOLIA project's creation of guidelines and training resources.

Context

We include all openly available educational and training materials on AI ethics that meet the eligibility criteria outlined below. There are no restrictions on the geographical origin of the materials or on the institutional sector in which they were produced (e.g., academic, professional, policy, or non-governmental organizations). The review primarily targets English-language materials, although relevant non-English resources will be included when accessible. Only materials published from 2022

onward are considered to ensure feasibility and relevance in this rapidly evolving field. This review will be conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) guidelines (Tricco et al., 2018).

Eligibility criteria (inclusion/exclusion criteria)

Category	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Topic relevance	Clear and substantive focus on AI ethics	AI content without an ethics component; general ethics content not sufficiently related to AI
Type of studies	Academic publications that provide or explicitly link to openly accessible educational resources on AI ethics (e.g., lesson plans, modules, training materials)	Academic publications that discuss AI ethics without linking to or including teaching resources; educational materials that are not openly or readily accessible (e.g., available only upon request, behind paywalls, or requiring institutional access).
Type of materials	Educational materials on AI ethics with defined learning objectives or outcomes, such as syllabi, modules, lessons, and assessments (e.g., MOOCs, OERs, slide decks, quizzes, assessment videos, web modules, case studies, infographics, podcasts, gamified learning platforms).	Informational resources without defined learning objectives or instructional design (e.g., single video lectures, opinion pieces, blogs)
Accessibility	Freely and openly available (no paywall) and directly accessible; e.g., Open Educational Resources	Paywalled content, “freemium” (essential features locked), time-limited access
Target audience	Materials designed for higher education students and/or professionals working with AI and ethics	General public
Language	Primarily English; non-English studies included if relevant or with English translation available	Primarily English; non-English studies included if relevant or with English translation available
Period	Published within the past three years (2022-present)	Older materials
Intent	Clearly intended for teaching or training, with interactive components that support reflection. Structured materials, referring to content that includes components like learning outcomes, clearly organized modules, and assessments.	No clear instructional goal or pedagogical structure. Purely informative.
Quality (second phase, after inclusion)	Created by reputable sources (e.g. universities, NGOs, expert individuals)	Unverified (user-generated) content lacking credible backing

Originality (second phase, after inclusion)	Unique, original content	Duplicated or mirrored from another included source
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Information sources

To ensure comprehensive scope of openly available AI ethics educational materials, multiple sources of evidence will be consulted. These include established academic databases, grey literature repositories, targeted online searches, and expert input from the AIOLIA consortium. Restricting the search to academic sources alone would risk overlooking relevant teaching and training materials, since many open educational resources are developed and distributed by universities, NGOs, professional associations, and industry partners outside traditional publishing channels.

- Academic databases: Web of Science and Google Scholar
- Grey literature from open educational resource repositories and institutional websites
- Web-based and non-indexed content located via targeted web searches (Google Advanced Search)
- Expert consultation with academic and industry partners from the AIOLIA consortium

Search

The search strategies were piloted at the end of August 2025. Draft strings were refined iteratively and discussed within the author group until consensus was reached. The Google Advanced Search strategy was developed in consultation with an expert from the Digital Methods Initiative at the University of Amsterdam, ensuring methodological rigor in the approach to web-based evidence.

Web of Science search string:

TI=(“artificial intelligence” OR AI OR “machine learning”) AND TI=(training OR trainer OR teach* OR course OR module OR e-learning OR learn* OR educat* OR lesson OR tutorial OR workshop OR webinar OR MOOC OR OER OR curriculum) AND TI=(ethic*)

Google Scholar and Google Advanced Search

Searches in Google Scholar will be limited to the .com domain. In both Google Scholar and Google Advanced Search, results will be restricted to the first 100 hits, following Miake-Lye et al. (2025), to balance feasibility with capturing relevant studies. Google Advanced Search will be conducted using the Search Engine Scraper tool, developed by the Digital Methods Initiative at the University of Amsterdam (UvA), within a Mozilla Firefox browser configured for research purposes (e.g., cleared cache, no personalization, stable search engine settings).¹ Both searches will use the following search string:

((“artificial intelligence” OR “machine learning”) AND (“training” OR “trainer” OR “teaching” OR “course” OR “module” OR “e-learning” OR “learning” OR “education” OR “educational” OR “lesson” OR “tutorial” OR “workshop” OR “webinar” OR “MOOC” OR “OER” OR “curriculum”)) AND (“ethics” OR “ethical”))

Selection of sources of evidence

¹ <https://digitalmethods.net/>

Screening will be conducted by a team of three reviewers. To ensure consistency, an initial pilot screening round (approximately 10% of records) will be carried out to test the clarity and feasibility of the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Based on this pilot, the criteria may be refined inductively by consensus within the review team before proceeding to full screening. In the main screening phase, titles and abstracts will be independently screened by two reviewers, with any disagreements resolved through discussion and, if needed, consultation with the third reviewer. The process will be documented in a PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (Page et al., 2021). Following an initial round of coding based on the inclusion criteria, a second phase quality and originality assessment will be carried out using a structured quality assessment form for educational materials.

Data charting process

Data charting will be conducted using a structured Excel sheet that includes fields for each data item. All three reviewers will be involved in the process. To begin, a pilot extraction will be conducted on approximately 15-20% of the included materials, with at least two reviewers independently charting each item. The pilot will be used to test the clarity of the data items and to refine the extraction framework inductively in consultation with the broader author group. For the main charting phase, the materials will be divided across the review team, with regular cross-checks and discussions to ensure consistency. Any modifications to the framework will be documented and agreed upon by the team before proceeding to full charting.

Data items

The data charting form will begin with a set of preliminary items structured as follows:

- Metadata: title, source, material type, year, accessibility, licensing, audience, and application domain
- Pedagogical approaches and learning strategies
- Learning objectives, competences or skills enhanced, and AI ethics concepts addressed
- Assessment features
- Tools

To pilot the extraction form, a sample of 15-20% of the included materials will first be charted. Alongside the predefined metadata, this process will help identify any additional relevant data items. The list of items will then be refined, following the principles of conventional qualitative content analysis (Green & Thorogood, 2018), in consultation with the broader author group, and may be further adjusted during the full review. After final inclusion, all materials will also be assessed for educational quality and originality.

Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence

No formal critical appraisal will be conducted, as the purpose of this scoping review is to map available educational materials rather than evaluate methodological quality.

Data synthesis and presentation of results

Further meetings with the author group will be held to resolve any remaining questions about data charting. Once data extraction is complete, the categories will be clustered and organized into a matrix. Results will be presented in tables and figures where appropriate, in addition to narrative synthesis, to provide a clear overview of the characteristics and diversity of the included materials. The final synthesis and presentation of results may be adapted depending on the nature of the data, and will be determined in consultation with the author group and decided collectively.

Expected outputs

The expected outputs of this study will be: **1)** this scoping review protocol; **2)** project reporting (as part of deliverable 4.1); **3)** a peer-reviewed review article; and **4)** an openly available dataset of the included materials and their coded characteristics as supplementary material with the published article.

Review timeline

Start date: 1 November 2025. End date (completion of search, screening, and extraction): 31 January 2026. Preparation and publication of the review article will follow thereafter.

Ethics approval

Not applicable

Funding Declaration and Competing Interests

The AIOLIA project is funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement 101187937. The review team declares that there are no competing interests.

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